

TRANSIENT ANALYSIS OF LAYERED COMPOSITE SUBJECTED TO DYNAMIC INPLANE IMPACT LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a composite laminate with n layers subjected to dynamic inplane impact loading on the surface as shown in Fig. 1 is investigated in detail. Complete solutions of each waves is expressed in an explicit form. In analyzing this problem, the reflections and refractions of stress waves must be taken into account, which will generate infinite waves on each composite layer. The transient responses of stresses and displacement in the transform domain on each layer are expressed in a closed form.

Keywords: Composite Layered Laminate, Dynamic Impact Loading, Transient Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The propagation of stress waves through an unbounded medium is not a difficult subject. If the boundary is introduced, however, reflected waves will be generated from the free surface, making the problem more complicated. The classical analysis in this area was first proposed by Lamb [1]; he considered the half space subjected to point and line loads on the surface of a semi-infinite half space. Since this early analysis of Lamb, a great many contributions have appeared, pertaining to what is commonly referred to as Lamb's problem. Buried source problems are of considerable interest in seismology and have been studied by many investigators; including Lamb. Nakano [2] analyzed the buried line dilatation source in a half space, but he failed in generalizing his harmonic steady state results to transient solutions. Lapwood [3] re-studied Nakano's problem, and later Garvin [4] also solved Nakano's buried line dilatation source problem by using a suitable distortion of the Ω contour suggested by the work of Cagniard. In Garvin's paper, the numerical results are limited to surface displacement due to a dilatation source, and the generated waves in the medium are incident P waves, reflected PP waves and PS waves. Recently, Tsai and Ma [5] obtained the complete transient solutions of buried dynamic point forces and displacement jumps for an elastic half space.

The applications of composite materials have grown very rapidly for the last two decades because of their high strength and light weight. Composite materials have been widely used in aeronautical industries to replace metals in aircraft structures for the purpose of weight saving. The methods to find the response of composite laminates under various conditions have appeared to be of most significant concern in this field. A good understanding of their static and dynamic behavior under various loading conditions is needed. For static analysis, this has already received widespread attention in the last two decades. However, the study of transient response just starts to grow in recent years.

Wave propagation in layered media should be studied extensively because of its wide technological applications. Harmonic waves in composites with isotropic layers were studied by Sun et al. [6], Stern et al. [7], Hegemier and Nayfeh [8], Hegemier and Bache [9] and Nemat-Nasser et al. [10]. Transient plane waves propagating in a periodically layered elas-

tic medium were examined by Ting and Mukunoki [11], Mukunoki and Ting [12] and Tang and Ting [13]. In studying the wave propagation in a layered medium, various approximate theories have been proposed to predict the dynamic response. Most of the approximate theories can predict satisfactorily the frequency equation due to a sinusoidal oscillation [6-9, 14], and some can also predict the late-time asymptotic solution in a semi-infinite layered medium due to a step load applied at the boundary.

Because of the difficulty in analyzing the transient response of infinite number of reflected and refracted waves in a layered composite structure. Only very few papers used the transient analysis to study the phenomena of the wave propagation in a layered medium. For transient waves, one could in theory obtain the solution by superimposing harmonic waves of all frequencies and all modes. This approach, however, is not practical and a more direct approach should be employed to study the transient waves. In this study, the transient response of applying an antiplane dynamic point force at the surface of an n layered composite laminate is investigated in detail. The material properties and the thickness of each layer are different. The analytical results obtained in this paper are exact and are expressed in a simple closed form, each mathematical term representing a physical transient wave.

2. STATEMENTS OF THE PROBLEM

Consider a stress-free composite laminate with n layers, each layer is made of different material and with different thickness as shown in Fig. 1. Each layer is assumed homogeneous and isotropic and perfect bonding is considered at the interfaces. Let layer 1 denotes the top layer on which the dynamic loading is applied and layer n is the bottom layer. A Cartesian coordinate system is defined in the body at the top face. The top face of the n layered composite lies in the plane $y = 0$ and $-\infty < x < \infty$. At time $t = 0$, a dynamic concentrated inplane force of magnitude σ_0 (per unit length in the z -direction) acts at $x = 0, y = 0$. The boundary conditions on top and bottom layers of the problem can be written as

$$\sigma_{yy}^{(1)}(x, 0, t) = \sigma_0 \delta(x) H(t) \quad \text{for} \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{yy}^{(n)}(x, -h^n, t) = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{xy}^{(1)}(x, 0, t) = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{xy}^{(n)}(x, -h^n, t) = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad (4)$$

where

$$h^n = \sum_{j=1}^n h_j,$$

in which h_j is the thickness of the j th layer, δ is the delta function and H is the Heaviside step function. Perfect bonding along the interface is ensured by the stress and displacement continuity conditions of each layer

$$\sigma_{yy}^{(i)}(x, -h^i, t) = \sigma_{yy}^{(i+1)}(x, -h^i, t) \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1, \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{xy}^{(i)}(x, -h^i, t) = \sigma_{xy}^{(i+1)}(x, -h^i, t) \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1, \quad (6)$$

$$u^{(i)}(x, -h^i, t) = u^{(i+1)}(x, -h^i, t) \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1, \quad (7)$$

$$v^{(i)}(x, -h^i, t) = v^{(i+1)}(x, -h^i, t) \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1. \quad (8)$$

The propagation wave in a homogeneous, isotropic elastic medium is governed by the two-dimensional wave equations

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} = b^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2}, \quad (10)$$

where

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\Lambda + 2\mu}} = \frac{1}{v_l},$$

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\mu}} = \frac{1}{v_s}.$$

Here μ and ρ are the shear modulus and the mass density of the material, respectively, Λ is the Lamé constant, a and b are the slowness of longitudinal and shear waves. Equations (9) and (10) are the uncoupled wave equations. Because of their associated modes of deformation, ϕ and ψ are referred to as the longitudinal and shear wave potentials. The displacements are derived from the potentials according to

$$u = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}, \quad (11)$$

$$v = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad (12)$$

where u and v are the displacements in the x and y directions. The stresses can be written in terms of the potentials by means of Hooke's law. The relevant components of the stress tensor can be written as

$$\sigma_{xx} = \Lambda \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} \right) + 2\mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x \partial y} \right), \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = \Lambda \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} \right) + 2\mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x \partial y} \right), \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = \mu \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \right). \quad (15)$$

This problem is solved by the application of integral transforms. Applying the Laplace transform of (9) and (10) over time and the two-sided Laplace transform over x . The solutions of the wave equation in the Laplace transform domain are given in layer (i) by

$$\hat{\phi}^{(i)} = A_i e^{p\alpha_i y} + B_i e^{-p\alpha_i y}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{\psi}^{(i)} = C_i e^{p\beta_i y} + D_i e^{-p\beta_i y}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\alpha_i = \sqrt{a_i^2 - \lambda^2}, \quad \beta_i = \sqrt{b_i^2 - \lambda^2},$$

in which p and λ are the variables of the one-sided and the two-sided Laplace transform parameters, respectively. Constants A_i , B_i , C_i and D_i are to be determined through the transforms of the boundary and continuity conditions.

3. TRANSIENT SOLUTIONS IN TRANSFORM DOMAIN FOR THE N LAYERED MEDIUM

This section is concerned with the derivation of the undetermined coefficients A_i , B_i , C_i and D_i in an n -layered medium. The relationship of unknown constants for the same layer and for the different layer can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_i \\ D_i \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_i \begin{bmatrix} A_i \\ C_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{i+1} \\ C_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}_{i/i+1} \begin{bmatrix} A_i \\ C_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{T}_i and $\mathbf{G}_{i/i+1}$ are 2×2 matrix and can be determined by the boundary and continuity conditions. We also have

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_i \\ D_i \end{bmatrix} \delta = \mathbf{H}_{i/i+1} \begin{bmatrix} A_i \\ C_i \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{F}_{i+1/i} \begin{bmatrix} B_{i+1} \\ D_{i+1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{i/i+1}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{i+1/i}$ are 2×2 matrix and are called reflected wave matrix and refracted wave matrix, respectively. From (18), (19) and (20), \mathbf{T}_i can be written as the following form

$$\mathbf{T}_i = \mathbf{H}_{i/i+1} + \mathbf{F}_{i+1/i} \mathbf{T}_{i+1} \mathbf{G}_{i/i+1}.$$

The expression

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{i+1} \\ C_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{H}_{i+1/i} \begin{bmatrix} B_{i+1} \\ D_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{F}_{i/i+1} \begin{bmatrix} A_i \\ C_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (21)$$

can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{i+1} \\ C_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{i+1/i} \mathbf{T}_{i+1})^l \mathbf{F}_{i/i+1} \begin{bmatrix} A_i \\ C_i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Hence, we get

$$\mathbf{G}_{i/i+1} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{i+1/i} \mathbf{T}_{i+1})^l \mathbf{F}_{i/i+1}, \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_i = \mathbf{H}_{i/i+1} + \mathbf{F}_{i+1/i} \mathbf{T}_{i+1} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{i+1/i} \mathbf{T}_{i+1})^l \mathbf{F}_{i/i+1}. \quad (24)$$

The reflected wave matrix $\mathbf{H}_{i/j}$ can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{H}_{i/j} = \frac{1}{R_{i/j}} \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

where

$$R_{i/j} = 4\lambda\alpha_i\alpha_j\beta_i\beta_j(1-\gamma)^2 + \lambda^2[\beta_i^2 - (1+\gamma)\lambda^2 + \gamma\beta_i^2]^2 + \gamma(\alpha_i\beta_j + \alpha_j\beta_i)b_i^2b_j^2 + \alpha_i\beta_i[\gamma\beta_j^2 + \lambda^2(2-\gamma)]^2 + \alpha_j\beta_j[\beta_i^2 + (2\gamma-1)\lambda^2]^2, \quad (i, j \text{ no sum}) \quad (26)$$

in which

$$\gamma = \mu_j / \mu_i$$

and

$$a = \{4\lambda^2\alpha_i\alpha_j\beta_i\beta_j(1-\gamma)^2 - \lambda^2(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + \gamma\beta_i^2)^2 + \gamma(\alpha_i\beta_j - \alpha_j\beta_i)b_i^2b_j^2 + \alpha_i\beta_i(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^2)^2 - \alpha_j\beta_j(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 + 2\gamma\lambda^2)^2\} \Phi_1,$$

$$b = \{4\lambda\alpha_j\beta_i\beta_j(\gamma-1)(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 - 2\gamma\lambda^2) + 2\beta_i\lambda(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 - \beta_i^2 + \lambda^2)(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^2)\} \Phi_2,$$

$$c = \{4\lambda\alpha_i\alpha_j\beta_j(1-\gamma)(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 - 2\gamma\lambda^2) + 2\alpha_i\lambda(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^2)(\beta_i^2 - \gamma\beta_j^2 - \lambda^2 + \gamma\lambda^2)\}\Phi_3,$$

$$d = \{4\lambda^2\alpha_i\alpha_j\beta_i\beta_j(1-\gamma)^2 - \delta\lambda^2(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 - \gamma\beta_j^2 + \gamma\lambda^2)^2 + \gamma(\alpha_j\beta_i - \alpha_i\beta_j)b_j^2b_i^2 + \alpha_i\beta_i(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^2)^2 - \alpha_j\beta_j(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 + 2\gamma\lambda^2)^2\}\Phi_4,$$

$$\Phi_1 = \begin{cases} e^{-2p\alpha_i h_i} & \text{if } i < j \\ e^{2p\alpha_i h_j} & \text{if } j < i, \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi_2 = \Phi_3 = \begin{cases} e^{-p(\alpha_i + \beta_i)h_i} & \text{if } i < j \\ e^{p(\alpha_i + \beta_i)h_j} & \text{if } j < i, \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi_4 = \begin{cases} e^{-2p\beta_i h_i} & \text{if } i < j \\ e^{2p\beta_i h_j} & \text{if } j < i. \end{cases}$$

The refracted wave matrix $\mathbf{F}_{i/j}$ can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{F}_{i/j} = \frac{1}{R_{i/j}} \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} e &= 2\alpha_i b_i^2 \{\beta_j(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 + 2\gamma\lambda^2) + \beta_j(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^2)\}\Phi_5, \\ f &= 2\beta_i \lambda b_i^2 \{2\alpha_j\beta_j(1-\gamma) + \gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 - \beta_i^2 + \lambda^2\}\Phi_6, \\ g &= 2\alpha_i \lambda b_i^2 \{2\alpha_j\beta_j(\gamma-1) + \gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 - \beta_i^2 + \lambda^2\}\Phi_7, \\ h &= 2\beta_i b_i^2 \{\alpha_j(\beta_i^2 - \lambda^2 + 2\gamma\lambda^2) + \alpha_i(\gamma\beta_j^2 - \gamma\lambda^2 + 2\lambda^2)\}\Phi_8, \end{aligned}$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_5 &= \begin{cases} e^{p(\alpha_j - \alpha_i)h_i} & \text{if } i < j \\ e^{p(\alpha_i - \alpha_j)h_j} & \text{if } j < i, \end{cases} \\ \Phi_6 = \Phi_7 &= \begin{cases} e^{p(\alpha_j - \beta_i)h_i} & \text{if } i < j \\ e^{p(\beta_i - \alpha_j)h_j} & \text{if } j < i, \end{cases} \\ \Phi_8 &= \begin{cases} e^{p(\beta_j - \beta_i)h_i} & \text{if } i < j \\ e^{p(\beta_i - \beta_j)h_j} & \text{if } j < i. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

From the boundary condition of the n th layer, we have

$$\mathbf{T}_n = \mathbf{H}_{n/n+1}$$

where

$$\mathbf{H}_{n/n+1} = \frac{1}{R_n} \begin{bmatrix} [4\lambda^2\alpha_n\beta_n - (\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2)]e^{-2p\alpha_n h_n} & -4\lambda\beta_n(\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2)e^{-p(\alpha_n + \beta_n)h_n} \\ 4\lambda\alpha_n(\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2)e^{-p(\alpha_n + \beta_n)h_n} & [4\lambda^2\alpha_n\beta_n - (\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2)]e^{-2p\beta_n h_n} \end{bmatrix},$$

in which

$$R_n = 4\lambda^2 \alpha_n \beta_n + (\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2)^2.$$

From the boundary condition of the first layer, we can obtain

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ C_1 \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{1/0} \mathbf{T}_1)^j \begin{bmatrix} (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)/p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \\ -2\lambda \alpha_1 / p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \end{bmatrix},$$

where

$$\mathbf{H}_{1/0} = \frac{1}{R_1} \begin{bmatrix} 4\lambda^2 \alpha_1 \beta_1 - (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)^2 & -4\lambda \beta_1 (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2) \\ \delta 4\lambda \alpha_1 (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2) & 4\lambda^2 \alpha_1 \beta_1 - (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)^2 \end{bmatrix},$$

in which

$$R_1 = 4\lambda^2 \alpha_1 \beta_1 + (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)^2.$$

4. TRANSIENT SOLUTIONS FOR THE TWO LAYERED MEDIUM

In the previous section, the solutions in the Laplace transform domain are constructed for general n layered medium. The transient full field solutions can then be obtained by Laplace inversion the solution in Laplace transform domain. In order to explain the methodology for constructing the infinite reflected and refracted waves generated at each layer. A two layered composite laminate is chosen to analyze the problem in detail. In this case we have $n = 2$ and

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ C_1 \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{1/0} \mathbf{T}_1)^l \begin{bmatrix} (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)/p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \\ -2\lambda \alpha_1 / p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ D_1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_1 \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{1/0} \mathbf{T}_1)^l \begin{bmatrix} (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)/p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \\ -2\lambda \alpha_1 / p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_2 \\ C_2 \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{2/1} \mathbf{T}_2)^l \mathbf{F}_{1/2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{1/0} \mathbf{T}_1)^j \begin{bmatrix} (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)/p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \\ -2\lambda \alpha_1 / p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (30)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_2 \\ D_2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_2 \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{2/1} \mathbf{T}_2)^l \mathbf{F}_{1/2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{1/0} \mathbf{T}_1)^j \begin{bmatrix} (\beta_1^2 - \lambda^2)/p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \\ -2\lambda \alpha_1 / p^3 \mu_1 R_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (31)$$

where

$$\mathbf{T}_1 = \mathbf{H}_{1/2} + \mathbf{F}_{2/1} \mathbf{T}_2 \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{2/1} \mathbf{T}_2)^l \mathbf{F}_{1/2},$$

$$\mathbf{T}_2 = \mathbf{H}_{2/3},$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{1/2} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\mathbf{H}_{2/1} \mathbf{T}_2)^l \mathbf{F}_{1/2}.$$

Each term in (28) represents propagating waves in the first layer and with the propagation direction along the negative y axis. Each term in (29) represents propagation waves in the direction toward the positive y axis for the first layer. The similar physical explanation is also applied for the unknown constants A_2 , B_2 , C_2 and D_2 in the second layer.

The remaining task is to evaluate the inverse transforms of this expression. The exact transient solution in time domain can then be found by inverting the Laplace transform by Cagniard-de Hoop method. The idea of the Cagniard-de Hoop method is to deform the path of integration in the λ -plane in such a manner that the inverse Laplace transform of the integral along the new path of integration can be obtained by inspection.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The difficulty in analyzing the transient response of a layered composite laminate subjected to dynamic impact loading is well known. Pure numerical method, such as finite element method, is usually used to investigate this problem. In this study, a methodology which is based on the mathematical analysis, is proposed to construct the transient solutions of a layered composite laminate which will generate infinite reflected and refracted waves in each layer. The Laplace transform method is used to construct the solutions in the Laplace transform domain. The Cagniard-de Hoop inverse method is performed, enabling us to investigate in detail the structure of the wave pattern and transient solutions in time domain.

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Figure 1. Configuration and coordinate system of a n layered composite structure.